

"Please hang in there!": User Acceptance as a Key Element for a Successful Charging Infrastructure

Katharina Csillak¹, Marisa Meta², Alexandra Appel¹, Laura V. Böhm¹, Divy Gupte¹, Florian Preusse¹

¹ Mobility Department,
Institute for Climate Protection, Energy and Mobility (IKEM),
Magazinstraße 15 – 16, 10179 Berlin, Germany

² FIT Consulting s.r.l.
Via Merulana 272, 00185 Roma

Katharina.Csillak@ikem.de / meta@fitconsulting.it

Abstract: With rising numbers of electric cars in Europe, there is a growing demand for planning tools. The H2020 project USER-CHI is meant to unlock the massive potential of electromobility in Europe by, among other things, designing electric charging networks around user needs. One such product is CLICK – a charging infrastructure planning tool. During the demonstration phase of CLICK, technical and user acceptance feedback was collected and will be evaluated in this paper. The evaluation will focus on possible drivers and barriers in the design of CLICK to optimize the spatial planning of charging infrastructure. In addition to the space requirements, the subjective perception and the resulting acceptance are of elementary importance for the success of nationwide availability of electric mobility and the (partial) substitution of cars with combustion engines. Evaluating CLICKs' user acceptance contributes to better identifying user needs and preferences. Hence, the tool can be developed in accordance with those needs and increase its attractiveness. The main research questions are: How satisfied are users with the current charging infrastructure planning tool CLICK? What opportunities and obstacles can be derived for the implementation of charging infrastructure?

Keywords: e-mobility, Europe, user acceptance, charging infrastructure, planning tools

1. Why User Acceptance Matters

The annual registrations for electric cars have been growing in Europe for years. They increased by about 50% from 2020 to 2021 alone [1]. The European Union (EU) supports that development by additionally introducing policies that incentivize the reduction of CO2 emissions [2]. Following those increasing numbers, the desire for a broader availability of charging points, and more interconnected charging infrastructure can be assumed. According to the Consumer Monitor 2022, one of the main barriers for battery electric vehicle (BEV) users is the overview of the public charging points and their user perception [3]. The increase in registrations of electric vehicles (EVs) also influences the total share of newly registered cars. From 2020 to 2021, there was an increase from 11% to 18% in the share of total new car registrations,[1] showing a growing demand for EVs. Correspondingly, there is also an increasing demand for user-friendly charging infrastructure. The Consumer Monitor 2020 reports that the range of BEVs was perceived as insufficient [3]. In connection with this, the demand for appropriate coverage of public charging infrastructure in adequate locations and with adequate technologies is given. Charging infrastructure planning tools will facilitate coping with this demand. Therefore, an existing

incentive exists for implementing a planning tool to plan charging infrastructure. The H2020 project “Innovative solutions for USER centric CHarging Infrastructure” (short: USER-CHI) acts in this field of transport planning.

The USER-CHI project is meant to unlock the massive potential of electromobility in Europe by, among other things, designing electric charging networks around user needs and deploying an interoperability platform. It does so by co-creating and demonstrating smart solutions around seven connecting nodes of the Mediterranean and Scandinavian-Mediterranean Trans European Network-Transport (TEN-T) corridors between February 2020 and January 2024. More precisely, those nodes along the TEN-T corridors are Barcelona, Berlin, Budapest, Rome, Turku, Florence, and Murcia. Eight products are developed during the project, including software applications, and knowledge-based platforms. One such developed tool is the Charging Infrastructure Location and Holistic Planning Kit, also known as “CLICK”. [4]

CLICK aims to be an easy-to-use question-and-answer online tool for the top-down location planning of charging infrastructure (www.click-platform.eu). Therefore, it supports users such as transport and city planners in meeting the growing demand for charging infrastructure. This paper refers to the intermediate first user demonstration version 0.4 of CLICK. CLICKs’ purpose is to optimize the location planning of new charging infrastructure in cities, matching the users’ needs, preferences, and habits, with the existing charging technologies available in the market. In order to obtain an outcome aligned with these principles, the user is requested to upload data. For that effort to be fruitful, user acceptance of the online tool is a prerequisite. CLICK analyses inputs provided by users (e.g., employees of municipalities, car-sharing companies, and housing companies) and estimates the optimum charging infrastructure to be deployed in the city. Furthermore, CLICK can be fed with actual utilisation data of charging infrastructure within individual planning areas. [5] This enables a post-planning process of monitoring the utilization, enabling demand-oriented expansion of the charging infrastructure network.

This paper is meant to evaluate the data collected from the user acceptance questionnaire and workshops of CLICK. [6] Its results contextualize with the future of charging infrastructure planning and the influence of user acceptance. In this regard, the main research questions are: How satisfied are users with the current charging infrastructure planning tool CLICK? What opportunities and obstacles can be derived for the implementation of charging infrastructure?

2. Methodology of User Acceptance

In this paper, user acceptance is defined as a scale of subjective assessment, measuring the users’ satisfaction with CLICK and its usability on various elements. The measurement of user acceptance is done through multiple measurement scales described in the USER-CHI methodology section (Chapter 2.2). The user groups are defined by their representation of real-world usage. The list of user groups of CLICK includes municipalities, private and commercial EV-fleet owners (e.g., car-sharing companies), and e-mobility planners (e.g., charging point operators (CPOs)). They are meant to replicate the targeted population as closely as possible to get information on how the software can be further improved. This chapter gives a short overview of the methodology for user acceptance.

2.1 Definition of User Acceptance

In general, “acceptance” is seen as the process or fact of something received as adequate, valid, or suitable for a person or a group of people [7]. In addition, “user acceptance” is defined more precisely in psychology as a person's attitude towards a product, technical system, or parts of a system. By attitude, mostly satisfaction, and usefulness are the main parts of it, as mentioned by van der Laan et al. (1997) definition of the user acceptance scale [8]. Therefore, methods related to this definition of user acceptance focus more on the satisfaction and usability of a product. Methods of measuring mostly come from the working fields of marketing, product testing, and software development. One example is the method of User Acceptance Testing (UAT). It is commonly used in software development and is sometimes called beta or end-user testing. In this development phase, the intended audience tests the software to emulate real-world usage. Its goal is to verify that the application will meet the end-users needs. It works with scenarios and data representative of actual usage in the field [9]. Besides UAT, methods measuring user acceptance differ depending on the researcher's context, background, and definition of the term acceptance.

This difference becomes clear when looking at evaluations in other H2020 projects. One example is the project MEISTER (2019-2022), which focused on new business models in environmental-friendly charging infrastructure. The user acceptance “*could not be substantiated by the Impact Assessment*” [10]. Still, it is described through increased usage figures, the number of registered users in the app, and a tenant survey, which asked for the tenants' satisfaction with the Park & Charge (P&C) offer [11]. It becomes apparent that user acceptance in MEISTER was defined through usage and satisfaction and measured through quantitative methods of the number of usage and standardized satisfaction questions (Likert scale). Another example is the H2020 project SCALE-UP (2021-2025). This project “*will aim to improve multilevel and multi-stakeholder governance enabling seamless multimodal transport*” [12]. It defines acceptance as the “*share of the target group favorably in receiving or approving the key elements of the mobility approach in the city*” [13]. Sometimes, the definitions of acceptance and awareness of transport services are quite close, and both include factors of satisfaction. However, there seems to be a focus on consent in citizens' acceptance. The methodologies will be surveys through different levels of the project (quantitative and qualitative). In summary, both projects show different approaches. One focuses more on usability and satisfaction, using quantitative data, and the other on feelings, emotions, and consent of a target group and includes additional qualitative data.

For USER-CHI and CLICK, satisfaction, and usability indicate user acceptance. In addition, these two aspects are strongly connected in the methodology of explaining user acceptance and influence one another. For example, in the kick-off workshop of USER-CHI, possible barriers that may negatively affect the perception of EVs, also in terms of user acceptance, were defined. Those include legal, infrastructural, financial, and transparency barriers [14]. They are meant to assist in the understanding of the current limitations and underutilized possibilities of a given product or service. In the context of CLICK, it means that due to user satisfaction being directly connected to the input of user data, improving its limitations through implementing the gathered feedback from the side of the users, it directly and positively influences its possibilities. Conversely, this means that the acceptance of CLICK relies on the users' understanding and handling their possibilities, knowledge, and data input. There is a strong connection here throughout the satisfaction of the entire process of creation and use. Explaining the methodologies used in the project (see chapter 2.2) is therefore significant to understanding the paper and speaking about acceptance of the product.

2.2 USER-CHI Methodology

The analysis of user needs and patterns for requirement definitions for USER-CHI was concluded in an early project stage [15]. These identified patterns build the basis of evaluation on user acceptance. The methods were re-used to measure user acceptance in the first test phase of CLICK, whose results will be presented in this paper (see Chapter 4). Therefore, explaining the methodologies used in the project is significant in discussing the importance of user acceptance in the charging infrastructure.

As an early step, usage scenarios to demonstrate USER-CHI products have been created in WP1 (2020). According to the product leaders, these scenarios were requirements to evidence innovations related to the products, interests, expectations, capabilities, and facilities of the project cities. Usage patterns have been defined to cover the products that must be demonstrated to end users and intermediate users, including CLICK [16].

Based on this preliminary work, three main methods were used for collecting feedback on the user acceptance [17], those being: TAM, SUS, and NPS. The **TAM (Technology Acceptance Model)** [18] was developed to explain how the perception of utility and ease of use influences users' attitudes to technology and its effect on usage decisions. Its objective is to assess the USER-CHI products, such as CLICK, regarding fulfilling requirements and demands, finding alternatives, choosing options, and exploring more opportunities. Furthermore, to assess the usability of the USER-CHI solutions, a ten-item scale named **SUS (The System Usability Scale)** [19] is utilized, giving a global view on subjective usability assessments. It uses a one-to-four or one-to-five Likert Scale (I disagree to I agree). For its ease of use, the respondents' opinion on the feature(s) of a product or service is measured. For example, by asking if they (dis-)agree on the sentence: “I would need the support of a technical person to use CLICK.” The third method is the **NPS (Net Promote Score)**. [20] It is a customer loyalty and satisfaction measurement in which customers are asked how likely they are to

recommend a product or service. This happens on a scale of zero to ten. It serves the purpose of finding out whether the user base increases enough through personal recommendations or if further efforts must be made.

In summary, all three methods were used for CLICK in two steps: workshops (qualitative) and a questionnaire (quantitative). CLICK gathered technical feedback in workshops (online/ in person) as a first step. In those sessions, the participants were guided through the entire planning process, focusing on evaluating the tool and its results. Ultimately, the city partners could individually conduct the entire planning process and navigate through the tool. The feedback was collected in minutes during feedback workshops or via e-mail from the 27th of April until the 9th of June 2023. As a second step, a user acceptance questionnaire collected feedback per participant right after the workshop. The questions were based on the three main methods described earlier (TAM, SUS, and NPS). The demonstration phase of CLICK is currently still ongoing and will finish at the end of September. For this paper, the feedback from the workshops and questionnaire of the first part of the demonstration phase (April to June 2023) is being evaluated.

3. First Results of User Acceptance of CLICK

The feedback results are separated in reference to their source: workshops (Chapter 3.1) and the user acceptance questionnaire (Chapter 3.2).

3.1. – Results from the workshops

The feedback from the workshops included responses from users in Barcelona, Rome, Turku, Budapest, Florence, and Murcia. It is mainly technical feedback, referring to the functionality, usability, and results created with CLICK. Regarding its functionality, users want to include more points of interest and dynamic variables in the tool. Regarding usability, the users were asking for more clarifications on handling CLICK and the calculations running in the background.

Murcia, Barcelona, and Rome particularly wanted more explanations on how CLICK calculates the results. Regarding handling, Rome was unsure how to upload data files such as metro stations and existing charging poles. At the same time, all mentioned cities were uncertain how each variable is weighted in the calculation. Another point addressed that different types of public transport stations should not be considered equal in the calculation. Barcelona added that the tool should first ask for the type of charging poles needed and then calculate the number of charging points. Other feedback concerned the recommended number of poles, which was considered too low by several cities. For the users, it was also unclear how private space was defined. Several cities also had issues with the data upload. For Barcelona, it was unclear how to upload inhabitants per district and individual road types, while Murcia was unsure about citizens' data. Budapest would provide maps from geo information systems (GIS) rather than using Open Street Map (OSM) information. Nevertheless, the OSM in-load option was seen as a positive feature of CLICK. A technical issue was identified when Rome wanted to upload map files, which were too large for the server. Creating a shared account option (so all people in the same city can work on a shared file) was also mentioned.

According to all the cities, more points of interest (POIs) should be added in CLICK. Mentioned POIs are, e.g., restaurants, public parks, malls, and offices. Additionally, aspects like the ratio of the charging type (AC, DC, or HPC) or the amount of EVs should be individually adjustable. Several cities also mentioned that there should be more opportunities to type in individual data, such as numbers and percentages, for the strategy details. All in all, the cities received CLICK very well, and they were eager to test and evaluate the tool to customize it for their purposes. CLICK has already created a big interest in Finnish municipalities, and the city of Turku will introduce them to the tool. On the other hand, Budapest wants to use CLICK to develop a new e-mobility concept.

3.2. – Results from the User Acceptance Questionnaire

The participant's background was asked in the first part of the questionnaire. The main part of the questionnaire then focused on the usability of CLICK and the workshops conducted. The rating scale reached 1 = "I disagree" to 4 = "I agree".

Table 1. User Acceptance Questionnaire result in the format: value (amount of same value answers)

Question Scale 1-4, 1= low/I disagree. 4= high/I agree	Average	Highest	Lowest
1) Overall Impression on CLICK	3,33	4 (4)	2 (1)
2) Would like to use CLICK in the future	3,22	4 (6)	1 (1)
3) Features of CLICK are unnecessarily complex	1,56	4 (1)	1 (6)
4) Would need the support of a technical person to be able to use CLICK	2,11	4 (1)	1 (3)
5) Too much inconsistency in the handling of CLICK	1,44	2 (4)	1 (5)
6) CLICK will improve my planning performance	3,00	4 (2)	1 (1)
7) CLICK will increase my productivity	2,67	4 (2)	1 (1)
8) Learning how to use CLICK is easy	3,67	4 (6)	3 (3)
9) I have the necessary skills to use CLICK	3,11	4 (3)	2 (2)
10) I intend to be a heavy user of the CLICK system	2,33	4 (1)	1 (2)
11) The webinar was easy to follow	3,67	4 (4)	3 (2)
12) How easy was it to use CLICK for locating new charging infrastructures compared to similar tools?	2,86	4 (3)	1 (2)
13) How likely would you recommend the CLICK solution to a colleague Scale 1-10, 1= I would not recommend. 10 = I would highly recommend	8,78	10 (4)	7 (3)

Overall, CLICK is perceived as an easy-to-use and easy-to-learn tool. It is considered quite consistent and shows the potential to improve performance and productivity. Nevertheless, at this stage of CLICKs' development, not all participants would heavily use CLICK for infrastructure planning. On the other hand, most participants would at least likely recommend CLICK to a colleague.

Moreover, the results of the questionnaire revealed two special cases. In one case, a participant would not consider using CLICK as it would not increase productivity. In total, this participant voted for the lowest on four questions (1,2,6,7), while being among the lowest ratings on another three questions (3,4,10). Despite these answers suggesting no interest in CLICK, the participant would still highly recommend the tool (10 out of 10 on question 13). One can assume that this person, being a project manager, might not have to use the tool oneself, but recommend it to coworkers due to the ease of use.

In the other case, a participant had difficulties utilizing the tool offered and did not consider his/her skills adequate. This participant rated two questions among the lowest (8,9), five questions among the highest (1,2,5,12,13), and on two questions, the participant rated the single highest (3,4). Nevertheless, the participant would highly recommend CLICK, as stated in question 13 (10 out of 10). This could also be interpreted as the person in the position of project manager who is not comfortable with using planning tools. However, the participant agrees with the ease of usage of CLICK and would highly recommend the tool to others.

Those two cases portray opposite perspectives, coming to the same conclusion. With the first one being seemingly very knowledgeable in planning and rating CLICK low on their personal usage, the second one seems to lack the necessary skills to be effectively using CLICK. But both agree with CLICK being easy to understand and would both highly recommend the tool to their coworkers.

4. Conclusion for the Charging Infrastructure Planning

This paper evaluates users' satisfaction with the charging infrastructure planning tool CLICK in a first testing phase. While many academic studies paid attention to the user-friendliness of the Planning Support System (PSS), relatively few studies have investigated the utility of using PSS in planning practices [21] [22]. In USER-CHI, the decision to combine the System Usability Scale (SUS) methodologies to assess the tool's usability, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) to evaluate perceived usefulness, and the Net Promote Score (NPS) to deviate potential future tool usage is aimed at addressing the gap in literature. In addition, the conduction of workshops with the users enables better identification of specific issues related to tool usage, and enriches the numerical assessment provided by SUS, TAM, and NPS.

Regarding user acceptance, CLICK already received valuable feedback in the first part of the demonstration phase. The users from the partner cities gave precise feedback on the functionality (more points of interest and more

dynamic variables), usability (more clarifications on the handling of the tool and the algorithms used), and results. The cooperation with the cities was achieved through a live workshop at the 6th USER-CHI consortium meeting in Turku, several organized online workshops, and ad-hoc meetings. The constant exchange with the cities led to new perspectives and insights on the CLICK tool.

In conclusion, user acceptance represents the strengths and weaknesses of CLICK at the same time. From the UAT, the authors concluded that feedback might differ depending on the position and background of a participant. The feedback from the user acceptance questionnaire and the feedback from the workshop still have limitations from using standardized methods. As user acceptance input is based on one's personal interpretation of the scaling and answer, standardized methods would make further work difficult. Not using standardized methods allows for flexible interpretations of its outcome for further development, and the work direction of it would depend on who reads the results. Additional qualitative interviews for more detailed feedback are recommended, especially regarding user satisfaction. Validation through counterpart questions is still needed. While using multiple methods can provide such validation, the possibility of repetitive questions is something to be aware of.

Furthermore, a conflict between accessibility and flexibility must be worked on as there is a risk of integrating feedback, which can cause a decrease in user acceptance through a form of survivorship bias [23]. More useability could lead to a lower quality of user experience, or lower useability could come with a more satisfying experience. It is important to note that the tool is still a work in progress, which could continuously influence the process. The feedback received so far mainly suggests changes to CLICK, rather than mentioning what is already perceived as well-functioning. This lack of positive feedback can potentially change aspects of the tool that were not desired to be changed by the users. Therefore, in the second part of CLICKs' demonstration phase, it should also be asked for positive feedback from the users. In this way, the developers of the tool know which aspects to work on and which aspects to maintain.

User-friendliness and perceived usefulness are interconnected and interdependent, and the results of this study confirm this. However, evaluating both remains relevant because they address different usage questions and needs. For instance, when considering the initial planning phase, these stages are more about sharing knowledge among various professionals involved rather than making technical decisions. In this regard, when using CLICK, someone who is not an expert in planning charging infrastructure will be highly interested in the ease of tool use, transparency of underlying model assumptions, and the readability and credibility of the outputs. If these requirements are met, the user would be more inclined to recognize its validity and accept its use. In more advanced planning phases (e.g., when speaking about AC/DC/HPC charging stations), for users who may already have experience with other PSS, the evaluation of usefulness becomes more critical, and the focus shifts more towards the validity of results in relation to local specific sociodemographic, legal, and environmental conditions. The need for data standardization, which would facilitate processing in tools like CLICK, is a well-known issue and is not addressed in this paper. In this sense, we acknowledge that the potential of artificial intelligence in handling non-standardized data is significant. However, the use of AI in the context of user acceptance of tools has yet to be considered.

With this paper, the importance of user acceptance for charging infrastructure planning should hopefully become more understandable when speaking about user-centric products, especially in mobility. Related mobility behavior changes are a critical part of the mobility transition to reduce emissions in transport. The demonstration and development phase of CLICK is special and very fruitful, as it includes diverse test users from different countries and with different positions and backgrounds. The constant exchange with those users helps to customize a tool that municipalities, housing companies, charging point operators, and many more can use in the future as the need for planning tools is growing. The city of Turku has already introduced CLICK to other Finnish municipalities that expressed their interest, and Budapest wants to develop a new e-mobility concept with CLICK. This study analyzed the results of the data collected during the first part of the CLICKs' demonstration phase, which will end in October 2023. The next step in this regard could be to assess the tools' development by verifying if the charging infrastructure planned with CLICK matches existing charging infrastructure plans.

It is important to note that the tool is still under development, and the user acceptance analysis is ongoing to reflect the users' demands in the final version of CLICK. Therefore, user acceptance is and will always be important when developing planning tools. It is especially important to remember how positive user experience leads to a positive feedback loop, while negative user experience can lead to a downward spiral. So "please hang in there" - in this

case, user acceptance becomes a make-or-break issue on whether a product in the developing field of supporting tools flourishes or gets overshadowed.

References

1. European Environment Agency Homepage, <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/topics/in-depth/electric-vehicles>, last accessed 2023/07/31
2. European Environment Agency: Electric vehicles in Europe (2016)
3. Vanhaverbeke, L., Verbist, D., Barrera, G.: Consumer Monitor 2022, European Commission, https://alternative-fuels-observatory.ec.europa.eu/system/files/documents/2023-06/2022%20EAFO_CountryReport_NL_0.pdf, last accessed 2023/09/26
4. Seidel, C.: Click Requirements and targets (2021)
5. Seidel, C., Gougam, I.: D2.3: CLICK software prototype integration report and demonstrator (2023)
6. Seidel, C., Gougam, I., Preuße, F., Csillak, K.: D2.4 CLICK USER Support material (2023)
7. Oxford Languages Dictionary, [OxfordLearnersDictionaries.com](https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com), last accessed 2023/09/05
8. Dorsch Lexikon der Psychologie, <https://dorsch.hogrefe.com/stichwort/nutzerakzeptanz>, last accessed 2023/09/05
9. Stanford University Homepage, <https://uit.stanford.edu/pmo/UAT>, last accessed 2023/09/05
10. Blankschein, M., Kallmeyer, F., Gonzalez, M., Csillak, K., Sabouni, A.: MEISTER IMPACT Assessment Report, p. 69 (2022)
11. Blankschein, M., Kallmeyer, F., Gonzalez, M., Csillak, K., Sabouni, A.: MEISTER IMPACT Assessment Report (2022)
12. SCALE UP project information, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/955332>, last accessed 2023/09/05
13. Engels, D., Wachter, E.: SCALE UP Evaluation Plan 1, In: Alario, R., Kunasvirta, A., Kiviluoto, K., Van Acker, S. (eds), p.78 (2022)
14. IBV: Presentation Kick-Off Workshop USER-CHI, Brussels, February 5th (2020)
15. Giménez, J., López, A., Soriano, C.: Usage Scenarios (2021), <https://www.userchi.eu/publications/>, last accessed 2023/09/05
16. Giménez, J., López, A., Soriano, C.: D1.2 Usage Scenarios for validating low-medium and high range charging system (2020, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/875187/results>, last accessed 2023/09/05
17. UserSense website, <https://www.usersense.io/usability-testing/analysis>, last accessed 2023/09/08
18. acceptance lab website, <https://acceptancelab.com/technology-acceptance-model-tam>, last accessed 2023/09/07
19. usability.gov website, <https://www.usability.gov/how-to-and-tools/methods/system-usability-scale.html>, last accessed 2013/09/08
20. Qualtrics website, <https://www.qualtrics.com/experience-management/customer/net-promoter-score/>, last accessed 2023/09/08
21. Brömmelstroet, M.: PSS are more user-friendly, but are they also increasingly useful? Transportation Research Part A - Policy and Practice, 104, 96-107 (2017), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2016.08.009>, last accessed 2023/09/11
22. Pelzer, P.: Usefulness of planning support systems: A conceptual framework and an empirical illustration, Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice (2017)
23. Brown, S., Goetzmann, W., Ibbotson, R., Ross, S.: Survivorship bias in performance studies. American Economic Review. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/31126889_Survivorship_bias_in_performance_studies, last accessed 2023/09/26